

Head motion elicited by viewing affective pictures as measured by a new LED-based technique

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Abstract

The complex sensory input and motor reflexes that keep body posture and head position aligned are influenced by emotional reactions evoked by visual or auditory stimulation. Several theoretical approaches have emphasized the relevance of motor reactions in emotional response. Emotions are considered as a tendency or predisposition to act that depend on two motivational systems in the brain –the appetitive system, related to approach behaviors, and the defensive system, related to withdrawal or fight-or-flight behaviors. Few studies on emotion have been conducted employing kinematic methods, however. Motion analysis of the head may be a promising method for studying the impact of viewing affective pictures on emotional response. For this purpose, we presented unpleasant, neutral and pleasant affective pictures. Participants were instructed to view the pictures and to remain still. Two light-emitting diodes (LEDs) were attached to the foreheads of participants, and a Wii Remote controller, positioned 25 cm away, detected the position of the LEDs in the medial-lateral and anterior-posterior axes. We found more sway in response to unpleasant pictures. In addition, unpleasant pictures also provoked faster movements than both neutral and pleasant pictures. This response to unpleasant pictures, in contrast to pleasant ones, might reflect the readiness or predisposition to act. Our data also revealed that men moved faster than women, which is in accordance with previous findings related to gender differences.

Emotional response is a set of neural, physiological, behavioural and subjective changes. Accordingly, motor reactions are a part of these changes and it might be useful and appropriate to explore the effects of affective stimuli on human motor behaviour further.

Several theoretical approaches have emphasised the relevance of motor reactions in emotions, from the classical fight-or-flight reactions (Cannon, 1929; Selye, 1936) to more recent approaches (Leventhal, 1984; Prinz, 2004). According to Lang and co-workers (Lang, 1995; Lang and Bradley, 2010; Lang, Bradley, and Cuthbert, 1997), emotions are considered as a tendency or predisposition to act that depend on two motivational systems in the brain – the appetitive system, related to approach behaviours, and the defensive system, related to withdrawal or fight-or-flight behaviours. Following this model, two basic bipolar dimensions have been proposed to describe emotions -affective valence, related to the dominant motivational system, and arousal, related to the intensity of activation of the motivational systems (Lang et al., 1997). This approach offers, therefore, a starting point to study body movements as markers of emotion or predisposition to act.

In this line, it has been found that viewing emotional pictures provokes slight postural and head position changes that, in turn, trigger compensatory movements to maintain an upright position (Azevedo et al., 2005; Ciria et al., 2017; Hillman, Rosengren, and Smith, 2004). Most of the time, maintaining the body posture and head position is automatic and has a reflex nature. The vestibular, visual, and somatosensory signals are encoded in a widely distributed brain system to elicit swift motor commands to keep upright balance (Dalton et al., 2017; Lopez, 2015). To date, however, few studies on emotion have employed kinematic methods to explore emotion-related postural changes, and the data are not always consistent. A posturographical study by Azevedo and coworkers (2005) showed that viewing unpleasant (mutilation) pictures provokes less sway in medial-lateral direction than neutral and pleasant (sport) pictures, an effect that they called “freezing-like posture”. Similarly, Facchinetti, Imbiriba, Azevedo, Vargas, and Volchan (2006) also found that unpleasant (mutilation) pictures provoked less sway in medial-lateral direction than neutral pictures, but, in

addition, they also found that pleasant (families) pictures provoked less sway in anterior-posterior direction than neutral pictures. The results obtained by Stins and Beek (2007) also revealed an effect of emotion on the centre of pressure on a force platform, such that pictures of mutilation provoked less sway, but only in unipedal stance. More recently, Eerland, Guadalupe, Franken, and Zwaan (2012) found that participants staying on a force platform approached pleasant pictures (unconsciously leaned forward) and avoided unpleasant pictures (unconsciously leaned backwards) while they performed an unrelated task that required lateral movements. It has also been found that affective faces elicit postural changes, with faces reflecting happiness and pain provoking more body sway in the AP direction than neutral faces (Gea et al., 2014). In addition, these changes are independent of the sensory modality of the affective stimuli. For example, a recent study using auditory affective stimuli has also found more postural sway amplitude in the AP direction associated with unpleasant stimuli (Chen and Qu, 2017).

These results of kinematic properties applied to the study of emotion-related postural changes show that motion analysis of the head may be a promising method for studying the impact of affective pictures, since human head position is related to postural control and balance (e.g., Bronstein, 1988; Hollands, Sorensen, and Patla, 2001; Pozzo, Levik, and Berthoz, 1995). In the same vein, a recent paper (Ciria et al., 2017) reported a strong correlation between head movements and the postural control as measured by a platform pressure system. Motion analysis consists of recording the location of a point of the body in two or three dimensions over time, as well as measuring the speed of the motion, through a transmitter (infrared or light-emitting diodes, LEDs) attached to the surface of the point under study and a special video camera that records the light emitted by the transmitter. We used this method to record the sway and the speed of head motion provoked by the perception of affective pictures, based on head position - as indicated by one LED and recorded by a receptor- under the assumption that head movement is related to general postural changes.

From previous research (Azevedo et al., 2005; Facchinetti et al., 2006) we expected that unpleasant pictures would provoke a smaller magnitude of lateral displacement than the other affective contents, and pleasant pictures would elicit a smaller magnitude of displacement than neutral pictures. Research has found gender differences in several physiological responses elicited by affective stimuli. For example, women respond with greater defensive reactivity to unpleasant pictures, regardless of specific content, whereas appetitive activation increases in men only when viewing erotica (Bradley, Codispoti, Cuthbert, and Lang, 2001). However, research on posturography has not usually studied this factor. For example, Azevedo and co-workers (2005) and Mouras, Lelard, Ahmaidi, Godefroy, and Krystkowiak (2015) recruited all male samples. The studies that have included gender as a factor have found contrasting results. Hillman et al. (2004) found gender differences in the postural responses provoked by unpleasant pictures (men showed increased movement in anterior direction and women in the posterior direction), whereas Stins and Beck (2007) found no such differences provoked by affective pictures. Hence, we also included this factor in order to explore the effects that this variable may exert on the sway and speed of head motion further.

Methods

Participants

A sample of 51 student volunteers (36 females and 15 males) aged between 19 and 29 (*Mean* = 21.02; *SD* = 2.34) participated in the study. All subjects gave informed consent and received course credits for participation in the experiment. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Materials and design

We used 113 photographic affective pictures¹ from the International Affective Picture System (Lang, Bradley, and Cuthbert, 2008) and the EmoMadrid affective picture database

(<http://www.uam.es/CEACO/EmoMadrid.htm>). Pictures were selected so as to comprise 3 categories varying in emotional content (unpleasant, neutral, and pleasant). It should be noted that, in contrast to other studies, we used a wide spectrum of pictures (mutilation, accidents, blood, war, fights, medical equipment, pollution, criminals, nature, money, food, erotica, sport, entertainments) that would provoke different unpleasant and pleasant emotions. Each category contained 36 pictures. Different sets of pictures of the “pleasant” category were prepared for men and women: each contained five pictures depicting opposite-sex erotica, and shared 31 identical pictures with the other set. Pictures were arranged in 9 blocks, with each block containing all 12 pictures of the same category, since previous research has found a relationship between the sampling duration and the reliability of the posturographic measures (e.g., Carpenter, Frank, Winter, and Peysar, 2001). Each picture was presented for 3s, so each block lasted 36 s. There was no interval between pictures within blocks. The interval between blocks was 20 s. We prepared three orders of quasi-randomised sequences of blocks such that two consecutive blocks of the same emotional content were not allowed.

In order to study the complexity of the pictures selected, we calculated two indices related to the complexity displayed in the images, sub-band entropy and edge density (Rosenholtz, Li, & Nakano, 2007), as well as the size of their JPEG-encoded files (in bytes; Chikhman, Bondarko, Danilova, Goluzina, & Shelepin, 2012). Statistical analyses did not reveal significant differences between the pictures of the three affective contents in any of these parameters, $F(2,112) = .68, p = .51$, $F(2,112) = 2.24, p = .11$, and $F(2,112) = 1.07, p = .35$, respectively.

Procedure

The participants stood in the experimental chamber in a straight upright position at a distance of 120 cm from a 19-inch monitor, which displayed the pictures in a full screen mode (28.9° in height x 36° in width). Two marks on the floor indicated the feet position. Participants were instructed to adopt a comfortable bipedal stance, with their arms hanging loosely by their sides, and

to view the pictures that would appear on the screen. In addition, they were also instructed not to move their feet from the floor marks. Two LEDs on a rubber band were attached to their foreheads. A Wii Remote controller (Nintendo, Japan) was positioned 25 cm above the LEDs (see Figure 1). Sensors were removed after the recording, and participants were then required to rate the affective valence and arousal of each picture using a computerized Likert scale in a free viewing time task. For this purpose, after each picture, a 9-point rating scale was presented separately for each dimension –for affective valence, 9 indicated highly pleasant and 1 highly unpleasant, and for arousal, 9 indicated high arousal and 1 low arousal.

INSERT FIGURE 1 ABOUT HERE

Data collection and reduction

We employed a LED-based technique validated in an experimental physics laboratory for object movements (Abellán, Arenas, Núñez, and Victoria, 2013). An infrared receiver (Wii Remote controller), positioned at 25 cm above the subject's head, detected the position of a LED located on the forehead. This system recorded the position of the LED in the medial-lateral and anterior-posterior axes in the square of 13.9×9.6 cm, with a spatial resolution of 0.2 mm in each axis. The receptor sent the data to the computer via Bluetooth. The data were sampled at 100 Hz, so the position of the LED was captured every 10 ms. A second LED, also attached to the subjects' forehead, blinked at the beginning of each block of pictures so that the beginning and the end of each block could be distinguished. The computer programs that presented the stimuli and registered the data were written especially for this experiment using the programming languages Visual Basic and Delphi, respectively (Figure 2).

INSERT FIGURE 2 ABOUT HERE

For the entire length of each block of pictures, we used two ways to calculate the sway and speed of head movements typically employed in posturography (e.g., OKB Ritm, 2011). The sway in the medial-lateral and anterior-posterior axes was calculated as follows:

$$Q_x = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2}{N-1}}, \text{ mm}$$

$$Q_y = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}{N-1}}, \text{ mm}$$

where X_i and Y_i are coordinates at a moment, \bar{X} and \bar{Y} are means of the position in each axis, and N is the number of points

The formula used to calculate the motion speed was

$$V = \frac{L}{T}, \text{ mm/s, where}$$

$$L = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sqrt{(X_{i+1} - X_i)^2 + (Y_{i+1} - Y_i)^2}, \text{ mm}$$

where X_i and Y_i are coordinates at a moment, N is the number of points, and T is the duration of a fragment.

Data analysis

All the statistical analyses were performed with the PASW19 statistical package (IBM, USA). Each dependent variable was analysed by a mixed model of repeated measures, 2 (Gender) \times 3 (Emotional content: unpleasant, neutral, and pleasant), with Gender as the between-subjects variable and Emotional content as the within-subjects factor. When appropriate, we applied a

Greenhouse-Geisser (ϵ) adjustment to the degrees of freedom to correct any potential inflation of the reported probability values. For the main statistical tests we obtained a measure of the effect size, partial eta-squared (η_p^2). Paired comparisons were performed with a Bonferroni correction (Keselman, 1998). The level of significance was .05. Lastly, the sample size needed to achieve a .80 power and an effect size $f = 0.4$ ($\eta_p^2 = .14$) was calculated with the G*Power software (version 3.1.9.2).

Results

Subjective evaluation

A significant main effect of Emotional content was found for affective valence ratings, $F(2, 98) = 435.50, p < .0001, \epsilon = .695, \eta_p^2 = .90$. As shown in Table 1, participants rated pleasant pictures with the highest affective valence; neutral pictures were rated with higher affective valence than unpleasant pictures (all $ps < .001$). We also found a significant main effect of Emotional content for arousal ratings, $F(2, 98) = 150.97, p < .0001, \epsilon = .695, \eta_p^2 = .76$ (see Table 1). Unpleasant and pleasant pictures were rated with higher arousal ratings than neutral pictures (both $ps < .001$).

INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Head motion

We found a significant main effect of Emotional content on the sway of head motion in the medial-lateral direction, $F(2, 98) = 3.21, p = .045, \eta_p^2 = .061$, significant linear trend, $F(1, 49) = 5, p = .030, \eta_p^2 = .093$. As shown in Figure 3, pairwise comparisons revealed that the amplitude of sway provoked by unpleasant pictures was marginally greater than that elicited by pleasant pictures ($p = .090$).

INSERT FIGURE 3 ABOUT HERE

We found no significant effect of Emotional content for the head motion in the anterior-posterior axis, $F(2,98) = .66$, $p = .32$, Gender, $F(1,49) = 2.56$, $p = .12$, or the interaction between both variables, $F(2,98) = .05$, $p = .95$.

We found a main effect of Emotional content on the speed of head motion, $F(2, 98) = 4.68$, $p = .012$, $\eta_p^2 = .087$, significant linear trend, $F(1, 49) = 6.54$, $p = .014$, $\eta_p^2 = .12$ (see Figure 4). Pairwise comparisons revealed that unpleasant pictures elicited faster head motion responses than neutral ($p = .032$) and pleasant pictures ($p = .041$).

INSERT FIGURE 4 ABOUT HERE

In addition, we found a main effect of Gender, $F(1, 49) = 4.78$, $p = .034$, $\eta_p^2 = .09$, showing that head motion was faster in men ($Mean = 9.12$; $SD = 2.05$) than in women ($Mean = 7.85$; $SD = 1.84$).

Discussion

The complex sensory input and motor reflexes that keep body posture and head position aligned are influenced by emotional reactions. We studied the effects of the emotional content of affective pictures on head motion during passive observation, since previous research has demonstrated a strong correlation between head movement and postural control (e.g., Ciria et al., 2017). For this purpose, we used a new procedure to record head motion, based on a LED placed on the head and recorded by an infrared detector.

Our results revealed an effect of emotional content on the medial-lateral sway of the head motion. However, contrary to our expectations, we found more sway in response to unpleasant pictures. This result contrasted with the data obtained by other researchers (Azevedo et al., 2005; Facchinetti et al., 2006), who found that unpleasant pictures provoked less sway in the medial-lateral direction. It has been proposed that this decreased motor reactivity is similar to both the so-called “freezing-like posture” usually displayed in the presence of a predator (Blanchard, Flannelly, and Blanchard, 1986), and the reaction of “fear of falling” (Carpenter, Frank, and Silcher, 1999). However, it is necessary to take into account that Azevedo and co-workers (2005) and Facchinetti and co-workers (2006) used only pictures depicting mutilations, and it has been demonstrated that these pictures provoke physiological and somatic responses that can be different from those elicited by other unpleasant pictures (Bradley et al., 2001; Sánchez-Navarro, Martínez-Selva, and Román, 2006; Sánchez-Navarro, Maldonado, Martínez-Selva, Enguix, and Ortiz, 2012). In our study, we employed a broader spectrum of unpleasant pictures, which could provoke different reactions and, therefore, a specific defensive head change could not be expected. It should be noted that other studies have shown that the freezing-like posture found by Azevedo and co-workers (2005) is not an exclusive reaction to unpleasant, mutilation pictures –for example, Hagenars, Stins, and Roelofs (2012) found a relationship between aversive life events and reduced body sway to unpleasant pictures. In this regard, it has been found that explicit sexual stimuli also provoke less sway motion than other neutral and pleasant contents (Mouras et al., 2015), though a recent study found greater head movement in the anterior-posterior axis, probably related to an approach response provoked by erotic pictures (Ciria et al., 2017). Further research is required in order to check whether different emotional contents within an affective category (e.g., unpleasant) provoke different motion reactions, as previous research on emotion has found in other psychophysiological indices (e.g., Bradley et al., 2001).

Our data also revealed that the speed of the head motion was influenced by the affective valence of the pictures. Unpleasant pictures provoked faster movements than both neutral and pleasant pictures. The faster response to unpleasant pictures might reflect the readiness or predisposition to act, since it may be related to a preparation for a fight-or-flight reaction. In the same vein, it has been proposed that in the process of natural selection it has been more important for survival to display a faster and stronger reaction to unpleasant stimuli than to pleasant stimuli. This phenomenon has been termed “negativity bias” (Cacioppo and Berntson, 1994; Cacioppo and Gardner, 1999). This reaction is usually accompanied by a general discharge of the sympathetic nervous system and endocrine secretion (e.g., noradrenaline), which facilitates energy mobilization and leads to a state of readiness for a motor reaction (Bradley et al., 2001; Sánchez-Navarro et al., 2006; Sánchez-Navarro et al., 2012; Cacioppo and Gardner, 1999). In contrast, pleasant stimuli, related to the appetitive motivational system, do not require an urgent response and may serve as a cue to pursue a goal or to explore the environment further (Baumeister, Bratslavsky, Finkenauer, and Vohs, 2001; Spielberg, Heller, and Miller, 2013). Our results on speed of movement might reflect, therefore, a behavioural bias prompted by unpleasant pictures.

Our data replicated previous findings regarding the effect of gender (e.g., Stins and Beek, 2007), since we did not find sex differences related to the sway of motion, even when using a greater spectrum of picture contents. However, motion speed clearly differed between men and women, with men moving faster overall. Interestingly, this corresponds with a well-known fact that men’s reaction time is shorter in standard visuomotor stimulus-response tasks (e.g., Der and Deary, 2006). This gender effect was probably related to differences in body composition and metabolism between men and women, such as body fat, muscle mass, muscle fibre diameter, heart size, or blood haemoglobin levels, among others (Blaak, 2001; Janssen, Heymsfield, Wang, and Ross, 2000; Miller, MacDougall, Tarnopolsky, and Sale, 1993; Pan and Habicht, 1991). Although these gender differences are in agreement with previous research, we must be cautious when interpreting these

data because of the difference in the sample sizes of men and women. Future research, therefore, should check for gender-related differences.

We should also note that we used a measurement of general bodily activation for each axis as a component of emotion. Another, fruitful, design would be to calculate the direction of head motion during each picture, which would require recording a baseline epoch before each picture (as in Hillman, 2004), which was not done in our design and should be taken into account in future research.

Overall, the method employed in our study - analysis of head motion during passive picture perception - has proved to be effective in studying emotional reactions and it reveals that unpleasant pictures provoke more motion sway and faster movement, especially in men. Further studies, however, are needed to ascertain the influence of specific affective stimuli or conditions (e.g., anger, disgust or happiness) on motor behaviour.

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Footnotes

¹Pictures used in the study were from:

- a) IAPS: unpleasant: 1525, 3062, 3100, 3150, 3280, 3530, 6200, 6210, 6260, 6370, 6315, 6415, 6530, 6821, 6834, 7380, 9050, 9120, 9160, 9300, 9423, 9452, 9570, 9600 9920, 9925, and 9911; pleasant: 2030, 2216, 2346, 4531, 4150, 4532, 4235, 4538, 4250, 4255, 4561, 4572, 4608, 4609, 4645, 4676, 4689, 5260, 5480, 5621, 7501, 8500, 8501, 8502, 5626, 5628, 5629, 7502, 8021, 8179, 8186, and 8200; neutral: 2038, 2102, 2190, 2214, 2393, 2396, 2480, 2499, 2512, 2514, 2745.1, 2840, 2850, 2870, 5510, 5535, 7000, 7002, 7025, 7034, 7035, 7036, 7055, 7056, 7059, 7161, and 9070;
- b) EmoMadrid: unpleasant: 0223, 0284, 0320, 0326, 0391, 0581 0327, 0376, and 0586; pleasant: 0129, 0218, 0260, 0269, 0379, 0397, 0399, 0435, and 0437; neutral: 5510, 5535, 6150, 7009, 7034, 7035, 7058, 7161, and 7179;
- c) The Internet: the rest of pictures.

Figure 1. Schematic representation showing the LEDs on the participant's forehead, the Wii remote control located above the LEDs and the monitor positioned in front of the participant.

Figure 2. An example of three trials (unpleasant, neutral and pleasant) of a participant. The initial coordinates were assumed as (0, 0) by subtracting the 1st value as a baseline from each value.

Figure 3. Sway of head motion in the medial-lateral direction according to the affective pictures (bars represent Mean \pm SEM).

Figure 4. The speed of the head motion depending on emotional content of pictures (bars represent Mean \pm SEM)

Table 1. *Means and Standard Deviations (in brackets) of the Subjective Evaluation of the Pictures*

Emotional content	Affective valence (1-9)	Arousal (1-9)
Unpleasant	2.63 (0.76)	6.21 (1.48)
Neutral	5.19 (0.25)	2.96 (1.35)
Pleasant	6.94 (0.73)	5.87 (1.24)